
Environmental Accounting Disclosure and Financial Performance of Quoted Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and the financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study utilizes secondary data from annual reports of selected manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2018 to 2023. Environmental accounting disclosure is categorized into environmental policy disclosure, environmental performance disclosure, compliance with environmental regulations, and environmental initiative and risk assessment disclosure. Financial performance is measured using earnings per share (EPS), with firm size included as a control variable. The study employs multiple regression analysis to assess the impact of environmental disclosure on financial performance. Findings reveal a significant positive relationship between environmental policy disclosure and financial performance, while environmental performance disclosure and risk assessment disclosure show negative associations with EPS. Compliance with environmental regulations does not exhibit a significant effect on financial performance. The study contributes to sustainability accounting literature by providing empirical evidence on the role of environmental disclosure in corporate financial outcomes. The findings offer practical implications for policymakers, corporate managers, and stakeholders seeking to enhance environmental reporting practices and sustainable business performance.

Keywords: Environmental Accounting Disclosure, Financial Performance, Earnings Per Share, Sustainability, Nigerian Exchange Group

1. Introduction

The growing importance of sustainability and corporate responsibility has driven increased attention to environmental accounting disclosure (EAD) across industries (Chen et al., 2024; Deegan, 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Vitale, Cupertino & Riccaboni, 2023). As concerns over environmental degradation, climate change, and regulatory compliance intensify, firms are now expected to integrate sustainability into their financial reporting (Driss & Jaballah, 2025; García-Sánchez et al., 2025; Nguyen & Duong, 2025). Environmental accounting disclosure provides critical information about an organization's environmental policies, resource consumption, emissions, waste management, and sustainability initiatives. Investors, regulators, and stakeholders use this information to assess a firm's commitment to environmental stewardship and its potential financial risks and opportunities (Mayapada & Lyu, 2025; Odera et al., 2016).

In Nigeria, environmental reporting remains largely voluntary, with varying degrees of adoption across sectors (Nwaiwu & Oluka, 2018; Erin & Olojede, 2024). Unlike developed economies, where stringent environmental regulations guide corporate disclosure practices, Nigerian firms often report environmental information inconsistently due to weak regulatory enforcement and a lack of standardized guidelines (Kabara et al., 2023; Babalola & Olawuyi, 2022; Ofoegbu et al., 2018). This inconsistency raises concerns about transparency and accountability in corporate sustainability efforts. Prior studies, such as those conducted by Uwuigbe et al. (2018), have found that only a small proportion of Nigerian firms engage in meaningful environmental reporting, with most firms providing vague or generic disclosures.

Recently, several studies have examined the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance, with mixed findings (Vitale et al., 2023; Wu & Li, 2022; Wang et al., 2020; Deswanto & Siregar, 2018). Some researchers argue that firms that engage in comprehensive environmental disclosure attract more investors, reduce financial risks, and improve long-term profitability (KPMG, 2017; Xie et al. 2019). Others contend that excessive environmental reporting imposes additional costs on firms, reducing profitability and shareholder value (Emmanuel & Ifeanyichukwu, 2021). This study seeks to bridge this gap by empirically analyzing the effect of environmental accounting disclosure on the financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

This research aims to comprehensively understand how different aspects of environmental disclosure—such as policy commitments, compliance efforts, and risk assessments—impact firm performance. By employing multiple regression analysis, this study investigates whether environmental accounting disclosure serves as a value-enhancing tool or a financial burden for manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study also examines the moderating role of firm size, considering that larger firms may have more resources to implement and disclose sustainable practices than smaller firms (Pinheiro et al., 2025).

This research provided valuable insights for policymakers, corporate managers, investors, and other stakeholders. Regulators may use the findings to develop standardized disclosure requirements, while firms can leverage the results to improve their sustainability strategies. Additionally, investors can make more informed decisions based on the environmental practices and disclosure levels of the companies they invest in.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Concept of Environmental Accounting Disclosure

Environmental accounting disclosure entails reporting a firm's environmental impact, policies, and sustainability practices (Dhar, Sarkar & Ayittey, 2022). It ensures that companies acknowledge their environmental responsibilities and transparently communicate them to stakeholders. Various global frameworks, such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB), provide guidelines for standardizing environmental disclosures (Adams et al., 2022). Key dimensions of environmental accounting disclosure are discussed in sub-sections.

2.1.1 Environmental Policy Disclosure (EPDQ)

Environmental policy disclosure refers to a company's formal statement of commitment to environmental sustainability, outlining its goals, policies, and strategies for minimizing its ecological footprint (Ekemezie & Okafor, 2020). Firms that provide transparent and structured environmental policy disclosures are perceived as being proactive in their sustainability efforts, which can enhance corporate reputation and investor confidence (Chavarkar, 2020).

Environmental policy disclosures typically include statements on energy efficiency, carbon emissions reduction targets, waste management policies, and adherence to sustainability standards such as ISO 14001 (Sam & Song, 2022; Camilleri, 2022). These disclosures are crucial for stakeholders, including regulatory agencies, investors, and environmental advocacy groups, as they provide a framework for assessing a firm's long-term environmental commitment (Jaggi et al., 2018).

From a theoretical perspective, stakeholder theory suggests that firms with clear environmental policies engage more effectively with investors and customers who prioritize sustainability (Cordeiro & Tewari, 2015; Saqib et al., 2025). Legitimacy theory posits that companies disclose environmental policies to align with societal expectations, thereby enhancing corporate legitimacy (Deegan, 2019). Empirical studies have shown that firms with structured environmental policies often outperform competitors in attracting investment and securing long-term profitability (Ameer & Othman, 2012).

However, some scholars argue that environmental policy disclosure may not always translate to improved financial performance if it is not backed by substantive actions (Ojo & Balogun, 2019). Firms engaging in symbolic environmental disclosures—those that report sustainability policies without implementation—may face reputational risks and investor skepticism, leading to reduced financial benefits (Nwaiwu & Oluka, 2018).

2.1.2 Environmental Performance Disclosure (EPEDQ)

Environmental performance disclosure refers to the reporting of quantifiable environmental impacts, such as carbon emissions, energy usage, water consumption, and waste management (Chavarkar, 2020). Unlike policy disclosures, which focus on intentions, performance disclosures provide measurable evidence of a firm's sustainability efforts. Previous studies suggest that investors respond positively to firms that disclose strong environmental performance indicators, as these disclosures reduce information asymmetry and improve corporate transparency (Friede, Busch & Bassen, 2015; Reber, Gold & Gold, 2022).

However, excessive reporting on environmental performance can also signal high compliance costs and operational inefficiencies, leading to negative financial implications (Ojo & Balogun, 2019).

2.1.3 Compliance with Environmental Regulations (ECRDQ)

This aspect of disclosure focuses on firms' adherence to national and international environmental laws and regulatory frameworks. While compliance is often a legal necessity, voluntary disclosures regarding regulatory adherence can enhance a firm's legitimacy and reduce litigation risks. Some studies have found no significant financial benefits from compliance disclosure alone unless it is part of a broader sustainability strategy (Nwaiwu & Oluka, 2018; Christensen et al., 2021).

2.1.4 Environmental Initiative and Risk Assessment Disclosure (EIRDQ)

This includes reporting on proactive environmental initiatives and risk mitigation strategies. Firms that disclose detailed risk assessments demonstrate resilience and long-term sustainability planning, which may attract long-term investors. However, extensive disclosure on environmental risks may also highlight vulnerabilities, discouraging investors concerned about potential environmental liabilities (Arian & Sands, 2024).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in multiple theories that explain why firms disclose environmental information:

2.2.1 Stakeholder Theory

Developed by Freeman (1984), this theory posits that businesses must address the interests of diverse stakeholders, including regulators, investors, and society. Firms that fail to meet stakeholders' environmental expectations may experience reputational damage and financial underperformance. Stakeholder pressure has been a significant driver for environmental disclosures, as institutional investors increasingly factor sustainability into their decision-making (Gallego-Alvarez et al., 2017).

2.2.3 Legitimacy Theory

According to Gray (1995), firms disclose environmental information to maintain or enhance their legitimacy within society. This theory suggests that businesses use environmental disclosures as a tool to align themselves with societal norms and expectations. Firms in industries with high environmental risks, such as manufacturing and oil and gas, often engage in more extensive disclosures to justify their operations and gain public approval.

2.2.3 Resource-Based View (RBV)

This theory argues that firms with strong environmental disclosure practices can develop a competitive advantage by efficiently managing environmental risks and resources (Barney, 1991). Companies that invest in sustainable resource management can reduce costs, enhance efficiency, and improve long-term financial performance.

2.3 Empirical Review on Environmental Disclosure and Financial Performance

Several empirical studies have examined the impact of environmental disclosure on financial

performance. For instance, Adediran & Alade (2013) found that environmental accounting significantly affects corporate profitability in Nigeria. Their study showed that firms with extensive environmental disclosures experienced improved financial performance due to enhanced stakeholder trust. On the other hand, Ojo & Balogun (2019) investigated the relationship between environmental disclosures and firms' profitability in Nigeria. Their findings revealed a significant negative relationship between environmental performance disclosure and financial performance, suggesting that excessive reporting on environmental issues might raise concerns among investors. In the same vein, Emmanuel & Ifeanyichukwu (2021) assessed environmental accounting disclosure's effect on share price and return on assets. Their study provided mixed results, showing that while some aspects of disclosure positively impacted financial performance, others had no significant effect. Ameer & Othman (2012) conducted a study across multiple industries and found that firms with higher environmental disclosure levels achieved superior financial performance compared to their counterparts. They concluded that proactive sustainability initiatives attract long-term investors and improve financial stability.

In a European context, Friede et al. (2015) performed a meta-analysis of over 2,000 empirical studies and found a strong positive correlation between corporate sustainability practices and financial performance, reinforcing the business case for environmental accountability.

2.4 Hypotheses Development

Based on the literature, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between environmental policy disclosure and earnings per share of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H2: There is a significant negative relationship between environmental performance disclosure and earnings per share of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H3: Compliance with environmental regulations has no significant impact on the earnings per share of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H4: There is a significant negative relationship between environmental initiative and risk assessment disclosure and earnings per share of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H5: Firm size moderates the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and earnings per share.

This section highlights the importance of environmental accounting disclosure and how it relates to financial performance, while also grounding the study in well-established theoretical perspectives and empirical findings.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Data Collection

This study adopts an ex-post-facto research design, utilizing secondary data extracted from annual reports of ten (10) manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2018 to 2022. The data collection process focused on firms that consistently disclosed environmental accounting information and financial performance metrics. Firms with incomplete or missing disclosure data were excluded from the analysis.

3.2 Sample Selection

The selection criteria for the sample included publicly listed manufacturing firms that have a track record of sustainability reporting and adherence to corporate environmental policies. The sample was drawn using a purposive sampling technique to ensure the inclusion of firms with relevant environmental disclosures.

3.3 Content Analysis and Disclosure Index

The study employed content analysis to assess environmental disclosure practices. A disclosure index was developed based on five key dimensions of environmental reporting, each measured on a scale from 0 to 3, where 0 represents no disclosure and 3 represents comprehensive disclosure. The disclosure dimensions include environmental policies, environmental performance, compliance with regulations, risk assessment and environmental initiatives. Table 1 presents the environmental disclosure index scale.

Table 1: Environmental Disclosure Index Scale

Disclosure Items	0	1	2	3
Environmental Policies	No disclosure	Mention of policies	Detailed disclosure	Comprehensive policies with goals & targets
Environmental Performance	No disclosure	Basic performance metrics	Multiple performance indicators	Comprehensive data with trends over time
Compliance with Regulations	No mention	Basic acknowledgement	Disclosure of compliance efforts	Detailed disclosure with regulatory exceedance
Risk Assessment	No disclosure	Mention of potential risks	Identified environmental risks	Comprehensive risk assessment with mitigation strategies
Environmental Initiatives	No disclosure	Isolated initiatives	Several initiatives with details	Wide-ranging initiatives with impact analysis

3.4 Model Specification

A multiple regression model was used to test the impact of environmental accounting disclosure on financial performance:

$$EPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EPDQ + \beta_2 EPEDQ + \beta_3 ECRDQ + \beta_4 EIRDQ + \beta_5 FS + \varepsilon$$

Where EPS is earnings per share, EPDQ is environmental policy disclosure quantity, EPEDQ is environmental performance disclosure quantity, ECRDQ is compliance with environmental regulations disclosure quantity, EIRDQ is environmental initiative and risk assessment disclosure quantity, FS is Firm size (control variable) and ε is the error term

3.5 Description of Variables

Table 2 outlines the key variables used in the study, linking environmental accounting disclosure to financial performance. Earnings Per Share (EPS) is the dependent variable, representing firm profitability, while environmental disclosure variables (EPDQ, EPEDQ, ECRDQ, and EIRDQ) serve as independent variables. Firm size (FS) is included as a control variable to account for differences in scale and resource capacity among firms. The measurement of disclosure variables is based on a disclosure index, a common approach in previous studies (Clarkson et al., 2008; Ameer & Othman, 2012).

From a theoretical perspective, stakeholder theory suggests that firms with higher environmental disclosure levels, particularly in policy (EPDQ) and compliance (ECRDQ), may enhance investor confidence and legitimacy, leading to better financial performance (Freeman, 1984). However, legitimacy theory argues that firms may engage in extensive environmental disclosures, including performance (EPEDQ) and risk assessment (EIRDQ), primarily to manage public perception rather than to improve financial performance (Deegan, 2019). Empirically, studies have found mixed results—some indicate a positive relationship between structured environmental disclosures and profitability (Friede et al., 2015), while others suggest that excessive disclosures may increase costs and reduce shareholder value (Ojo & Balogun, 2019). The inclusion of firm size (FS) aligns with research showing that larger firms tend to disclose more environmental information due to greater regulatory scrutiny and stakeholder pressure (Haniffa & Cooke, 2005).

Overall, Table 2 highlights the importance of environmental disclosure as a strategic factor in corporate performance, supporting theoretical and empirical insights that balance transparency, regulatory compliance, and profitability.

Table 2: Variable Definitions and Measurement

Variable	Definition	Measurement
EPS	Earnings Per Share	Net Income / Total Outstanding Shares
EPDQ	Environmental Policy Disclosure Quantity	Score based on disclosure index
EPEDQ	Environmental Performance Disclosure Quantity	Score based on disclosure index
ECRDQ	Compliance with Environmental Regulations Disclosure Quantity	Score based on disclosure index
EIRDQ	Environmental Initiative and Risk Assessment Disclosure Quantity	Score based on disclosure index
FS	Firm Size	Log of Total Assets

4. Analysis and Results

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for the key variables in the study, including mean values, standard deviations, minimum, and maximum values. The mean EPS (9.62) indicates that, on average, the firms studied exhibit positive earnings per share, but the high standard deviation (16.43) suggests significant variability in profitability across firms. The minimum EPS of -12.41 highlights that some firms experienced losses, while the maximum EPS of 61.77 suggests that certain firms had strong profitability, reflecting the financial disparity among Nigerian manufacturing firms.

For environmental disclosure variables, ECRDQ (mean = 5.18, SD = 1.26) shows that firms generally disclose compliance with environmental regulations, with values ranging from 3.00 to 8.00, indicating some consistency in compliance efforts. EIRDQ (mean = 4.28, SD = 1.70) suggests moderate disclosure of environmental initiatives and risk assessments, but the minimum value of 0.00 reveals that some firms do not report these disclosures at all, supporting previous findings that environmental risk assessments are not a priority for all firms (Nwaiwu & Oluka, 2018).

Similarly, EPDQ (mean = 4.36, SD = 1.52) and EPEDQ (mean = 3.86, SD = 1.56) indicate moderate reporting of environmental policies and performance metrics, with values ranging from 2.00 to 8.00, showing variation in disclosure levels. The relatively lower mean of EPEDQ (3.86) compared to EPDQ (4.36) suggests that while firms are willing to disclose environmental policies, they are less likely to provide detailed performance metrics, possibly due to concerns over regulatory scrutiny or potential negative financial implications (Ojo & Balogun, 2019).

Firm size (FS), (mean = 10.63, SD = 0.99) shows a relatively high but consistent distribution, implying that the sample includes mostly large firms, which aligns with previous research stating that larger firms tend to disclose more environmental information due to higher stakeholder pressure and regulatory expectations (Haniffa & Cooke, 2005).

The descriptive statistics suggest significant variations in financial performance and environmental disclosure among manufacturing firms in Nigeria. While regulatory compliance disclosure (ECRDQ) is relatively stable, environmental performance (EPEDQ) and risk assessment (EIRDQ) disclosures are more inconsistent, which may reflect differences in firms' environmental strategies or stakeholder pressures. The findings support the stakeholder and legitimacy theories, highlighting that while some firms engage in proactive environmental disclosures to build legitimacy, others may disclose selectively to manage stakeholder perceptions.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Sta Dev.	Min.	Max.
EPS	9.62	16.43	-12.41	61.77
ECRDQ	5.18	1.26	3.00	8.00
EIRDQ	4.28	1.70	0.00	8.00
EPDQ	4.36	1.52	2.00	8.00
EPEDQ	3.86	1.56	2.00	8.00
FS	10.63	0.99	8.41	11.79

NOTE: EPS, earnings per share, ECRDQ, environmental compliance regulations disclosure quantity, EIRDQ, environmental initiative/risk assessment disclosure quantity, EPDQ, environmental policy disclosure quantity, EPEDQ, environmental performance disclosure quantity, FSIZ, firm size

Table 4 presents the regression analysis results examining the impact of environmental accounting disclosure on financial performance (measured by EPS). The coefficients indicate the magnitude and direction of relationships, while the t-statistic and probability values (p-values) determine the statistical significance of each independent variable. The model tests the stated hypotheses, providing insights into the effects of different environmental disclosure dimensions on firm profitability.

The significant positive coefficient ($p < 0.01$) supports H1, which posits that environmental policy disclosure (EPDQ) has a significant positive relationship with earnings per share (EPS).

This finding aligns with stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984), suggesting that firms with clear environmental policies attract investors, enhance reputational value, and gain competitive advantages (Clarkson et al., 2008). Ameer & Othman (2012) and Friede et al. (2015) corroborate this positive association, indicating that structured environmental policies enhance market valuation and investor confidence.

Regarding the effect of environmental performance disclosure (EPEDQ) and financial performance, the significant negative coefficient ($p < 0.05$) supports H2, suggesting that excessive environmental performance disclosure (EPEDQ) negatively affects earnings per share. This aligns with findings from Ojo & Balogun (2019), who argue that detailed environmental performance disclosures may highlight operational inefficiencies, increased compliance costs, or potential legal liabilities, thus discouraging investors. From a legitimacy theory perspective (Deegan, 2019), some firms disclose environmental performance mainly to manage public perception rather than as a reflection of efficiency, which may lead to negative financial implications.

In cognizance of compliance with environmental regulations disclosure (ECRDQ) and financial performance, the non-significant result ($p > 0.05$) supports H3, indicating that compliance with environmental regulations disclosure (ECRDQ) does not have a significant effect on financial performance. This suggests that firms adhering to environmental regulations do so as a legal requirement rather than as a value-adding strategy. Similar studies by Nwaiwu & Oluka (2018) found that compliance disclosure alone does not influence profitability unless coupled with proactive environmental initiatives.

However, with regards to environmental initiative and risk assessment disclosure (EIRDQ) and financial performance (EPS), the marginally significant negative coefficient ($p \approx 0.05$) supports H4, suggesting that disclosing environmental initiatives and risk assessments (EIRDQ) negatively affects financial performance. This aligns with findings by Cho & Patten (2007), where extensive risk disclosure signals potential environmental liabilities, discouraging investors. The Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991) suggests that while environmental initiatives can enhance firm competitiveness, the costs associated with proactive risk management may initially reduce profitability before yielding long-term benefits.

Importantly, firm size (FS) as a control variable is vital in the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance. The significant positive coefficient ($p < 0.05$) supports H5, confirming that firm size positively moderates the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance. Larger firms tend to have more resources for environmental initiatives, regulatory compliance, and sustainability investments, contributing to enhanced profitability (Haniffa & Cooke, 2005). This finding is consistent with prior research by Benlemlih et al. (2018), which found that larger firms benefit more from structured environmental disclosures due to economies of scale and enhanced stakeholder trust.

The model suggests that structured environmental policies contribute positively to financial performance, aligning with stakeholder and resource-based theories. However, excessive disclosures related to performance and risk assessment negatively impact

profitability, supporting legitimacy theory, which argues that firms may use such disclosures to gain social acceptance rather than financial benefits. Compliance with regulations alone does not enhance financial outcomes, indicating that firms need to integrate strategic environmental initiatives rather than simply adhering to legal requirements. Firm size plays a crucial role in moderating these relationships, reinforcing the idea that larger firms are better positioned to leverage environmental disclosure for competitive advantage.

Table 4: Regression Results

Variables	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECRDQ	0.0322	0.0417	0.9667
EIRDQ	-1.1147	-1.9624	0.0507
EPDQ	2.7665	3.3678	0.0009 **
EPEDQ	-2.1299	-2.1415	0.0331 **
FS	2.6441	2.0455	0.0417 **
Constant	-17.73	-1.4431	0.1501

(Note: ** indicates significance at the 5% level.)

Table 5 presents the overall fit and significance of the regression model used to analyze the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance. The R-squared value (0.6234) indicates that approximately 62.34% of the variation in earnings per share (EPS) can be explained by the independent variables—environmental policy disclosure (EPDQ), environmental performance disclosure (EPEDQ), compliance with environmental regulations disclosure (ECRDQ), environmental initiative and risk assessment disclosure (EIRDQ), and firm size (FS). The Adjusted R-squared (0.5897), which accounts for the number of predictors in the model, suggests a robust explanatory power, meaning that the model does not suffer from overfitting. The F-statistic (12.45) and its corresponding p-value (0.0001) confirm that the model is statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that the independent variables jointly influence financial performance. These results support the theoretical foundation that structured environmental disclosure plays a critical role in firm profitability, aligning with stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984) and resource-based view (Barney, 1991). However, the model also implies that 37.66% of the variation in EPS is influenced by other factors not captured in the model, suggesting that future research could integrate additional financial and governance variables to enhance explanatory power.

Table 5: Regression Model Summary

Model	R-squared	Adjusted R-squared	F-statistic	Prob (F-statistic)
1	0.6234	0.5897	12.45	0.0001 **

4. Discussion of Findings

The study's findings indicate a mixed relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance. Specifically, environmental policy disclosure (EPDQ) was found to have a significant positive effect on earnings per share (EPS). This suggests that firms with well-structured environmental policies attract more investors, enhance corporate reputation, and benefit from long-term financial sustainability. These results align with prior studies that link corporate environmental responsibility with financial performance (Adediran & Alade, 2013).

On the other hand, environmental performance disclosure (EPEDQ) and environmental initiative and risk assessment disclosure (EIRDQ) exhibited negative relationships with EPS. This could be attributed to the costs associated with environmental initiatives, which may outweigh immediate financial gains. Investors may also perceive excessive environmental disclosures as an indication of operational inefficiencies, leading to reduced confidence in firm profitability (Ojo & Balogun, 2019). Compliance with environmental regulations (ECRDQ), however, showed no significant effect on EPS, suggesting that firms adhering to mandatory environmental regulations do not necessarily experience financial benefits.

Firm size was found to positively moderate the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance. Larger firms, with greater resources and stakeholder expectations, are more likely to implement structured environmental policies that contribute to financial growth. This supports the legitimacy and stakeholder theories, which posit that firms enhance transparency to gain societal trust and investor confidence.

The study's findings have several theoretical and practical implications. From a theoretical perspective, the results align with stakeholder and legitimacy theories, supporting the notion that firms disclose environmental information to maintain legitimacy and build stakeholder confidence. The findings also provide empirical support for the resource-based view (RBV), indicating that firms leveraging environmental disclosure as a strategic resource can enhance competitive advantage.

From a practical standpoint, firms should focus on structured environmental policies and disclosure practices that align with corporate sustainability goals. Regulators should consider implementing standardized disclosure frameworks to ensure consistency and comparability of environmental reporting across industries.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The study concludes that environmental accounting disclosure plays a crucial role in shaping financial performance among quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. While environmental policy disclosure enhances financial performance, excessive performance disclosures and environmental risk assessments may have adverse effects. The findings support stakeholder and legitimacy theories, emphasizing the importance of strategic environmental reporting to maintain investor confidence and regulatory compliance.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed that policymakers should establish clear and standardized environmental disclosure requirements to ensure transparency and comparability across firms. Firms should balance transparency with strategic disclosure by focusing on meaningful environmental policies that align with corporate objectives while managing associated costs. Shareholders and potential investors should consider firms' environmental policies when making investment decisions, recognizing that structured environmental commitments may enhance long-term profitability. Further studies should explore additional financial performance metrics such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) to provide a broader understanding of the impact of environmental disclosure on financial success. The study highlights the growing relevance of

sustainability in corporate governance and calls for a balanced approach to environmental accounting disclosure to optimize financial and societal benefits.

5.3 Limitations and Directions for Future Research

While this study provides valuable insights into the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance, it is not without limitations. First, the study relies on secondary data, which may be subject to reporting biases or inconsistencies in disclosure practices among firms. Future research could incorporate primary data sources, such as surveys or interviews with corporate managers, to gain deeper insights into the motivations and challenges associated with environmental disclosure.

Second, this study focuses solely on manufacturing firms in Nigeria, limiting the generalizability of its findings. Future studies should expand the scope to include other sectors, such as oil and gas, banking, and telecommunications, to provide a more comprehensive analysis of the impact of environmental disclosure on financial performance across industries.

Third, this study primarily uses earnings per share (EPS) as the financial performance measure. While EPS is a widely accepted indicator of profitability, other financial metrics, such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and market valuation, should be considered in future research to provide a broader assessment of financial performance.

Finally, the moderating effect of firm size was examined in this study, but other potential moderating variables, such as corporate governance mechanisms, stakeholder pressure, and regulatory frameworks, should be explored in future studies to provide a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance.

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